

Identity and Relationship Management

The Key to Safe, Secure ICT Infrastructure

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Abstract: After providing an overview of the issues of identity and identification, this paper provides a foundational framework for a transaction-based definition of relationship and a relational definition of identity. This approach points to a convergence between two technological streams of evolution and development: (1) the provision of a secure and dependable message and transaction infrastructure through the appropriate use of security technologies to construct identities, certificates and signatures and (2) the creation of domains of relationship management within and between enterprises, which has been referred to as the "hub and spoke" architecture or the "integration engine" and is the basis for the current ICT architecture of client facing, globalised enterprise.

1. Introduction

There are a number of different approaches to identity. The requirements of civil policing, for example, are best addressed by a concept of identity as the unique and indelible attribute of the individual, which can be reliably detected and read. In a world that delivers such identities, we can be sure who everyone is and we can check whether they belong to the list of those we trust or those we distrust. The only further requirements we have for our security is that our guards and our lists are reliable.

In the world of information systems, we have technologies that guarantee unique identifiers for our records and there is a strong temptation to assume a simple link between the attribute concept of identity, described above, with the occurrence of records in our systems. These seductive ideas are compounded when we consider technologies such as biometrics and smart cards to implement identity management systems. We assume that we can maintain one to one relationships between unique items in our systems and unique "items" in the world. The wide range of situations where this simplistic approach causes worries about dependability, effectiveness, privacy, data protection and human rights demand a more sophisticated and expressive concept of identity. In this paper we argue that this wider view of identity is one that is associated with concepts of relationship and transaction. Without this more expressive and realistic idea of what identity is, and how we use it, many of the promises of an Information Society underpinned by an infrastructure which delivers ambient, intelligent support, are politically and socially unreachable, irrespective of their technological or economic possibility.

2. Digital Identity-Management - What is it?

2.1 Many dimensions

Identity is usually defined as the distinct personality of an individual regarded as a persisting entity. Psychological and cognitive studies study what it is like to experience your own identity. Forensic approaches focus on the problem of identification. In social, political and economic contexts, however, the key notion of identity is as the means by which individuals are recognised (made distinct) by other individuals for the purpose of transactions and relationships. Identity is comprised of the many sets of information and memories which are used to validate our claims to be who we are: your face is part of your identity, as is other data about your person such as your finger print or retinal scan, your date and place of birth, your current address and the names of your parents, in fact anything that serves to distinguish you and thus serves as an identity attribute.

Why should we take care of identity, why should we manage it? In the real world, every day everyone of us gives away information about ourselves. We do it buying food at the supermarket, as well as during conversations, sometimes "playing" a little bit, hiding and revealing. We decide on the amount of information to reveal according to roles and situations. In free relationships individuals can choose their role and how much information to reveal to the other parties. In different relationships, different sets of identity attributes are communicated, as in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Identity Model

An identity attributes set can contain the basic data of a person, e.g. the name, the number of the identity card or the address. Furthermore, an identity attribute set can also contain further, more or less dynamic, information about a person, such as political opinions, interests or functions [1]. A person can take different roles (e.g. professional and private ones) and therefore generate several identity attributes sets or profiles. The different profiles or "images", of a given individual are created when other people, institutions, enterprises or organisations become aware of individual identities and record information about them. Although we may demand the right of informational self-determination, we can not know the complete list of individuals or institutions who know us.

2.2 Getting online

In the online world, hiding and revealing is, in some respects, more difficult and in others easier. We can decide how much information to communicate about ourselves in the offline world. In the online world it is much more difficult to see exactly what information is being revealed. We leave digital tracks when we purchase a book or use a home-banking service. The right to an informational self-determination is threatened by dishonest use of these data. The possibility of chaining the information and the lack of international data protection regulations leads to uncertainty. Even more, technological complexity does not help: there is no single point of observation and policing of data during a transaction on the Internet. The German multimedia laws [2] make it possible to use a pseudonym instead of the real name. By the use of a pseudonym, a pseudonym owner can legally act and maintain some degree of data privacy. There is a requirement that the pseudonym is ultimately traceable to the individual. This use of digital pseudonyms is made possible by the use of a digital signature, often embedded in smart cards.

2.3 More government activities

The identity card we know today will be replaced in future by a new card that may contain more identity attributes, including biometrics. In Germany it is planned to integrate the fingerprint into the identity papers. The Homeland Security Act in the USA will require a fingerprint and iris scan on all entry visas [3]. Individual state policies and approaches are varied [4]: Switzerland and Austria have plans for the introduction of a digital identity [5].

2.4 We need a new architecture

For the most part, we do not know which data is being collected by which Internet provider, on whose behalf and for what purposes. Technologies such as the semantic web [6] increase the fear that personal behaviours will be tracked connecting the different data we leave online. On the other hand, the use of certain services requires the use of identity attributes to make Internet transactions easier and more accessible to the user. More and more privacy concerns come from the intensive plans of identity control and identification systems initiated by many governments in order to prevent attacks and illegal activities. There are many open questions: who is watching us and for what purposes? How and why should we trust them when they use technologies we do not control? How do we balance our rights to privacy and freedom with the goals of the national security plans and of the private transaction management systems? To find answers to such fundamental questions, we need to define a new architectural framework, based not just on identity profiles storage and retrieval, but on the rich and diverse dimension and relationships that animate our life.

3. A new architecture: defining identity in terms of relationships

If we are to speak clearly about identity we need some definitions. We do not justify these definitions lexicographically although they do correspond to current usage. Our purpose is to define a useful and appropriate system to support our use of identity and, to do that we proceed by constructing composite ideas from simple ones and working with the composites to generate useful solution concepts. This utility has a price, however. If we are to benefit from it then we must make the ontological commitments of our basic definitions: we must accept the strict definitions, rather than loose informal ones, and stick to them.

First of all we define an event as an occasion when information is generated. Unique birth and death events delimit the existence of an individual who is capable of transacting

and having relationships. Our approach here must include real individuals, people or parties, and virtual or purely legal “individuals” such as companies or institutions.

An event becomes a transaction when it involves two or more individuals and produces intended changes in the distribution of resources and responsibilities among them. Interactions can produce unintended outcomes but, in this discussion, we are interested in what people intend in their social and economic activities.

When information from a previous transaction is used by the same parties in subsequent transactions, then we take the connected transactions to be a relationship. This definition of relationship implies:

- that multiple encounters happen among the same parties,
- that the parties recognise each other that the previous transactions are remembered and this makes a difference, e.g. the parties grow in trust.

An identity is the information used by parties to recognise each other, while an identifier is an information item (often a code) linking an identity to a history or set of records. The identity of a party may be entirely local to a transaction or to a relationship and not be linked to any other, public identity. In this case we call the relationship pseudonymous.

3.1 Register and index

The transactional concept of relationship and the relational concept of identity lead us to two useful implementation concepts: the register and the index. These concepts are not new and we would maintain that all we are doing is reframing how we talk about current practice in identity management and relationship management in order to have a more constructive discourse about the difficult policy and requirements issues which we have discussed in the first part of this paper. A register is a data structure under the control of a registrar who is responsible for ensuring that individuals have only one entry, with a unique identifier, that has attached to it an adequate, up-to-date set of data for the purposes of recognition and authentication. A registrar is, therefore, an identity provider. The cost of failure of registration or of authentication within a domain of application, dictates how elaborate the identification data set is and the care taken in its acquisition and maintenance.

Figure 2: The implementation of an index as a table

The data in a register (in this strict sense) has the sole purpose of distinguishing registered individuals. An index is a data structure under the control of a relationship manager. It is used to correlate local identifiers from the client records of members of a multi-agency partnership, domain or circle of trust. If the identifiers used by two different agencies for a particular individual are placed on the same row of an index by a relationship manager, then those agencies can communicate with each other about the subject.

An index is a data structure which may be distributed over the systems of the members of a partnership or circle of trust, corresponding to what Liberty Alliance call their business anchor lists [7] or could be held in a shared hub or front office system. An index (again in

this strict sense) only contains identifiers; it does not contain record information. Shared or public records are held in separate publication systems which are operated by or on behalf of the organisations who own and are responsible for the content. The local identifiers associated with a particular individual may appear on different rows of the same index and, in such cases, there can be no automatic communication possible between relationship suppliers regarding this subject; the relationship providers are unaware of the fact that they share a client.

3.2 Index publication and permissioning functions

Placing identifiers on the same row of an index is publishing the fact that certain relationships exist between relationship providers and a set of subjects. Access to an index generates the possibility of functions that implement consents and permissions for different transactions and relationship suppliers to talk to each other about a shared client.

The form of a permission could be the following:

- I, the client with relationship with service provider M, am willing to enter transactions with anyone who is a member of M's circle of trust.
- I, the supplier of relationship X will talk to anyone who has relationships Y or Z with my client.

Figure 3: Integrated relationship

These sentences are declarative and represent publications within a partnership or circle of trust. The result of such a publication will be a set of messages which are narrow-cast to the parties that share the indicated relationships with the subject and whose relationships have associated permissions i.e. the local identifiers for this client are entered in the same row of the index. These messages will only identify the subject to each party by means of their local identifiers within their relationship and the process preserves pseudonymity. Any sharing of information about mutually identified subjects would be part of a subsequent local transaction between the collaborating parties. The relationships entered into a particular row of an index are considered integrated. Any provider who has placed a local client identifier on a row can narrowcast requests for transactions regarding that particular client to any other providers on that row.

3.3 Relating many dimensions: the identity manager

We have noted that identifiers referring to the same individual may be placed on different rows of the same index thus creating uncorrelated local identifiers. We now introduce a special type of relationship supplier, the identity manager, who operates in the following way: if a client who has identities entered on more than one row of the index forms a relationship with an identity manager, any narrowcast message on any of the rows occupied by this client may be transferred to the relationship providers on the other rows under a set of local rules and permissions.

Figure 4: A Locally Managed Identity

3.4 Federated Permissioning

If we now introduce the concept of an identity manager who provides services to clients who have relationships in different index domains, partnerships or circles of trust, and who operates a further set of protocols and consents for routing client related narrowcast messages, we have a means of implementing a distributed and federal identity management infrastructure. This is represented in Figure 5.

In this scenario, our client has two relationships in each of two index domains, i.e. domains of trust and service co-ordination. Relationships Ra and Rc are integrated and their providers are able to share information and transactions. Relationship Rk and Rb are co-ordinated via identity manager A who implements a set of agreed local rules about which requests for which transactions are passed between them. The link between relationships Ra and c, on the one hand, and relationships Rk and b, on the other, are handled by a federal identity management service B which links relationship Rk to Ra and Rc creating a transaction request routing between the two domains regarding this client. Note further that identifiers a and c are mutually traceable because they were originally authenticated through register 1. Relationships k and b are not reliably traceable to each other outside of the identity and relationship management system because they are each based on authentications from different registers which use different attribute sets.

Figure 5: Federated Identity Management

4. Liberty Alliance and Passport

A number of Internet based identity management systems have been proposed and already implemented. We will briefly analyse here Microsoft Passport and Liberty Alliance. Both of these approaches are seeking to provide virtual ID-cards to users, which allow them to be identified or to use a single sign-on to multiple Internet services.

Microsoft Passport is based on the idea that every Internet user gets an online identity via a single authentication at the central Microsoft Passport service. This identity can be used to access the services offered by registered web sites.

In terms of our generalised identity management architecture, Microsoft Passport is a one register, one index configuration with a single third party identity manager implementing a user permissioned service. The permissioning, however, is implicit.

The Liberty Alliance takes a different approach to the Passport centralised one. Like that system, members of Liberty will issue ID-cards to Internet users, but without any identity attribute stored at a central place. The enterprises involved in the Liberty Alliance Project guarantee the correctness of the data of its customers to each other, using a federated approach. The Liberty Alliance approach ensures that the consumer is free to choose which enterprise will issue his card and for what services it will be used (e.g., airlines, banks or insurances).

In terms of our architecture, Liberty is a multi-register, multi-index approach. The Liberty Alliance standard is device independent and suitable for workstation computers, mobile telephones, television sets, cars and other devices. The standard is also compatible with credit, telephone and store cards. If an Internet connection is made using these cards, the consumer is immediately identifiable, ready to use the services.

5. Conclusion

The argument presented in this paper is that if we are to build identity management which is open to opportunities, delivers benefits but also takes care of our freedoms, then we must

base it on a concept of identity which is closely linked to that of relationship. We must maintain a distinction between the role of the registrar in creating and issuing identities, the role of the relationship manager in creating the contexts and spaces in which identities can be linked together and the role of the identity manager to ensure that such links respect the consents, rules, interests and preferences of the parties. By separating these roles and responsibilities, we have created an architectural framework in which possible approaches to identity and identification can be positioned and compared, particularly with respect to their reliance on centralisation versus federation. This framework has been developed in the context of the adaptation and deployment of current ICT enterprise infrastructures and identity management approaches to support public service and eGovernment. This has included social and health care, education and personal and economic development as well as the delivery of public administration functions to both the individual citizen, to families, communities and to companies [8]. In these contexts, the issues of identity have a far broader range of sensitivities and significances compared with the simpler world of commerce in which current developments are largely placed.

The identity architecture is a generalisation in which, both the emerging Liberty Alliance approach and the Microsoft Passport approach can be positioned and compared. It also indicates how current enterprise identity approaches need to be extended to accommodate the wider requirements of relationships of care, development and eGovernment. We have shown how, as an architectural framework, it is policy neutral and can accommodate a range of possible trust models and the range of possible policies of centralisation, federation and distributions of control. It is clear that the main obstacles to progress and, indeed, the agreement as to what might constitute "progress", in this area are political rather than technical. The technological component of this political discourse is important, however: the protagonists must have a realistic understanding what is possible and what consequences may be associated with any particular technical approach. But even more important is the requirement that the notions of identity upon which this political and architectural discourse is based are not narrowly determined, whether that determination is technological or political in nature. In this paper we have attempted the difficult task of plotting a conceptual space of identity, which is expressively adequate to represent the wide range of interests and concerns of the political, technical and social domains.

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